

Electroluminescent characteristics of Polymer and Quantum Dots nanocomposite Light Emitting Devices

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The development of organic devices has been driven by a growing demand for low-cost and flexible electronic devices. Polymer light-emitting devices (PLEDs) using solution processes can be promising candidates for large area, fast-response, and full-color flexible displays. Although a great deal of progress has been made in improving the luminous efficiency and lifetime of the solution-processed PLEDs since their discovery in 1990, the reliability of PLED devices is still much behind that of vacuum-deposited small-molecule based organic light emitting devices and still does not meet the requirements for commercialization toward full-color emissive displays.

The integration of organic and inorganic materials at the nanometer scale into hybrid optoelectronic structures enable active devices that combine the diversity of organic materials with the high-performance electronic and optical properties of inorganic nanocrystals. The optimization of such hybrid devices ultimately depends upon the precise positioning of the functionally distinct materials.

We have demonstrated the fabrication and characterization of hybrid polymer-quantum dot light emitting devices with the emissive composite film of PFO and inorganic CdSe/ZnS core/shell quantum dots (QDs). It is observed that both the electrical and optical characteristics are significantly improved by adjusting the thickness of the emissive layer. The device, with a configuration of indium-tin-oxide (ITO)/PEDOT:PSS/PFO:CdSe-ZnS/Ca/Al, had a turn-on voltage of 26V, the maximum luminance was 970 cd/m², and the maximum luminous efficiency 1.53 cd/A.

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